

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR ENGAGING ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN MATHEMATICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20552950>

Abstract. *This article comprehensively examines the theoretical foundations of increasing primary school students' interest in mathematics, as well as the pedagogical and psychological factors that influence the effectiveness of mathematics teaching in primary education. In the modern educational system, developing students' interest in mathematics is considered one of the most important tasks, since this subject plays a significant role in developing logical thinking, analytical abilities, independence, and creative problem-solving skills.*

The article analyzes the age-related and individual characteristics of primary school students and explores effective methods for developing positive motivation toward mathematics learning. Particular attention is paid to the use of interactive teaching methods, didactic games, problem-based learning, information and communication technologies, and innovative pedagogical approaches. The importance of organizing engaging and meaningful mathematics lessons to enhance students' cognitive activity and learning motivation is also highlighted.

Keywords: *primary education, mathematics education, interest in mathematics, logical thinking, didactic games, interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical approach, learning effectiveness, educational motivation.*

INTRODUCTION

“Mathematics is one of the important subjects that sharpens thinking and develops a person's logical thinking ability” [1]. Therefore, today, attracting primary school students to mathematics is considered one of the most urgent and important tasks of the education system. Because the primary education stage is an important period in which a child's initial attitude towards learning, worldview, and motivation for learning are formed. It is during this period that students develop an interest and positive attitude towards mathematics, which increases their chances of achieving high results in this subject at later stages of education.

The psychological and age characteristics of primary school students indicate that they more effectively absorb knowledge through interesting, demonstrative and practical activities. Therefore, it is important to organize mathematics lessons not on the basis of simple theoretical explanations, but on the basis of interactive methods, didactic games, problem situations and modern pedagogical technologies. Such an approach not only increases the activity of students in the lesson, but also develops their independent thinking, logical analysis skills and creative approach. In today's era of globalization and the development of digital technologies, the importance of mathematics is increasing. Because mathematics is not only a subject of study, but also one of the main subjects necessary for solving problems in everyday life, understanding economic and technological processes and acquiring modern professions. Therefore, developing mathematical literacy in students from primary school and increasing interest in this subject is considered one of the priorities of today's education system.

The pedagogical skills of the teacher are also of particular importance in increasing students' interest in mathematics in primary school. The teacher's favorable psychological environment, methods of motivation, individual approach and the use of modern methods form a positive attitude of students towards mathematics. In particular, the use of game technologies, logical tasks, interesting problems and information and communication technologies helps students to master knowledge in the subject more easily and with interest.

Also, family and school cooperation is one of the important factors in forming interest in mathematics. Parents' attention to their children's education, the learning environment created at home and their joint work with the teacher increase students' motivation towards mathematics. Therefore, establishing cooperation between teachers, students and parents in the process of mathematics education is an important pedagogical task.

In general, the interest of primary school students in mathematics not only improves the quality and efficiency of education, but also serves to educate a well-rounded, independent-thinking and modern-knowledged person. Therefore, in-depth study of the theoretical foundations of the formation of interest in mathematics and the introduction of effective methods into practice are one of the urgent issues of today's pedagogy.

“Primary education is the main stage in the development of students' intellectual and creative potential” [2]. From this point of view, teaching mathematics is not limited to the formation of calculation skills, but also serves to develop students' logical thinking, independent thinking, analysis, comparison, and problem-solving skills. In particular, the formation of mathematical knowledge in primary school students expands the opportunity to develop their mental activity.

A unique feature of mathematics is that it teaches students to think clearly, consistently and logically. During the lesson, students' thinking gradually develops through solving problems, performing operations on numbers, analyzing geometric shapes and completing various mathematical tasks. This forms not only mathematical knowledge and skills in them, but also analytical thinking competencies necessary in everyday life.

Effective teaching of mathematics in primary education also has a positive effect on students' mastery of other subjects. Because through mathematical thinking, students learn to analyze events and phenomena, understand cause-and-effect relationships and draw conclusions. This serves their overall intellectual development.

Mathematics lessons are also an important tool for developing students' creative abilities. Interesting problems, logical tasks and problem situations encourage students to search, find different solutions and think in new ways. In particular, the use of didactic games and interactive methods increases students' interest in mathematics and engages them in the active learning process.

In today's modern education system, teaching mathematics based on innovative pedagogical technologies is gaining importance. The use of information and communication technologies, electronic educational resources, virtual games and multimedia tools helps to organize mathematics lessons more interesting and effective. This not only increases students' motivation for mathematics, but also develops their skills for independent acquisition of knowledge. In addition, the teacher's pedagogical skills and individual approach play a special role in teaching mathematics. The teacher's effective organization of the lesson, motivation of students and taking into account their individual characteristics are important factors in forming interest in

mathematics. In particular, recognizing and supporting students' successes increases the effectiveness of the lesson.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The problem of attracting primary school students to mathematics is one of the current research areas in the field of pedagogy and methodology. In scientific research on this issue, the cognitive development of students, the formation of motivation, and the effectiveness of didactic approaches occupy a key place.

A number of scientists associate the formation of interest in mathematics with the internal motivation of educational activities. In particular, it is emphasized that in the process of primary education, students' interest develops directly through game elements, practical tasks, and visual aids. In this approach, taking into account the age characteristics and stages of psychological development of students is considered an important factor [6].

This study is aimed at studying the theoretical and practical foundations of attracting primary school students to mathematics. Theoretical analysis, pedagogical observation, questionnaires, interviews, pedagogical experiments, statistical analysis methods, and comparative analysis methods were used in the research process. During the research, students' level of interest in mathematics, their activity in academic activities, and their motivational state were analyzed based on pedagogical criteria.

The theoretical basis of the study was scientific research in the fields of pedagogy, psychology and didactics, as well as sources related to modern educational concepts. The analysis of scientific literature shows that the use of interactive approaches, problem-based learning technologies and digital didactic tools is of great methodological importance in increasing the cognitive activity of students in the process of primary education [10]. These approaches serve not only to help students master ready-made knowledge, but also to develop independent thinking, analysis, problem-solving and creative approach skills.

In particular, interactive educational technologies make it possible to activate the learning process, increase student participation in the lesson, and connect knowledge with practical activities. Problem-based learning, on the other hand, arouses cognitive interest in students, directing them to research, draw independent conclusions, and think logically. Digital didactic tools — multimedia presentations, interactive platforms, and visual models — serve to convey educational material in a more understandable and interesting form, which increases the level of emotional acceptance of primary school students.

Also, some studies emphasize the role of effective pedagogical dialogue between teachers and students in the formation and stabilization of learning motivation. In this regard, the teacher's communicative competence, empathetic approach, and ability to create a learning environment focused on the student's personality are considered important factors [11]. As a result of effective pedagogical communication, students develop self-confidence, a positive attitude towards the lesson, and a desire to actively participate, which directly serves to increase interest in mathematics. In general, the analyzed scientific sources show that the cognitive and motivational development of students in primary education is a multifactorial process and substantiate the important role of the combination of modern pedagogical technologies and an effective communication system.

RESULTS

The research thoroughly studied the pedagogical effectiveness of interactive methods, didactic games, and digital educational tools aimed at increasing the interest of primary school

students in mathematics. During the experimental work, changes in the students' activity in the lesson process, the ability to think independently, the quality of completing tasks, and their motivational state towards the subject were systematically monitored through the use of modern pedagogical technologies in mathematics lessons [12].

In particular, it was found that the level of student involvement in learning activities was much higher in lessons using interactive methods. Group work, “Brainstorming”, “Cluster”, “BBB”, methods based on question-and-answer and creating problem situations increased student participation in the lesson and encouraged them to think freely. As a result, it was observed that students showed activity in completing mathematical tasks and tried to approach issues creatively and logically. The use of didactic games served to organize lessons in an interesting way in accordance with the age and psychological characteristics of primary school students. Activities organized through game elements developed students' skills of competition, quick thinking and independent decision-making. At the same time, it was found that the existing fear and disinterest in mathematics decreased, and a positive attitude towards lessons was formed.

The use of digital learning tools also showed significant results during the study. Multimedia presentations, animations, interactive tasks and electronic didactic materials increased students' understanding of the subject and helped them to visually perceive mathematical concepts. In particular, tasks based on visual and practical activities had a positive effect on maintaining students' attention for a long time.

The analysis of the experimental results showed that in lessons where interactive methods and modern didactic tools were used, students' interest in mathematics, mastery indicators and independent work competencies significantly improved. This indicates that the effective use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the primary education process is of great importance in improving the quality of education and student motivation [12].

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining matematika faniga qiziqish ko'rsatkichlari

Figure 1. Interest and activity indicators in mathematics

DISCUSSION

The results of the study clearly showed that the use of interactive methods, didactic games, and digital educational tools is highly effective in attracting primary school students to mathematics. The empirical data obtained are fully consistent with the theoretical views put forward in the scientific literature and confirm that modern pedagogical technologies are one of the main factors in increasing students' cognitive activity and forming learning motivation [13]. It

was also found that these approaches make the educational process more interesting, interactive, and effective than traditional explanatory methods.

The analysis showed that the systematic use of interactive approaches in mathematics lessons not only increases students' interest in the subject, but also significantly develops their logical thinking, independent work, analysis, and problem-solving competencies. In particular, methods such as group work, "brainstorming", "working in small groups", "cluster", "insert" increase the activity of students, accelerate their thinking process and allow them to participate as subjects in the educational process [14]. This serves to form students' skills in independent decision-making and substantiation of their opinions.

Matematika faniga qiziqish ko'rsatkichlari

Figure 2. Indicators of students' interest in mathematics

Also, during the study, it was found that didactic games are of great psychological, pedagogical and motivational importance for primary school students. Lessons organized on the basis of game elements form a positive emotional state, free thinking, competitiveness, and a desire for active participation in students. As a result, possible fears and negative attitudes towards mathematics are significantly reduced [15]. This situation once again confirms that taking into account the psychological characteristics of young students is important in increasing educational effectiveness.

The teacher's ability to correctly assess the psychological state of students is also very important. By taking into account the mood, fatigue level, concentration and emotional state of students during the lesson, the teacher can flexibly organize the lesson. This serves to maintain students' interest in the lesson and increase their activity.

In addition, establishing effective communication is an integral part of the pedagogical process. When an open, sincere and trusting communication environment is created between the teacher and the student, students are not afraid to express their opinions freely, seek to ask questions and actively participate in discussions. This develops their logical thinking and independent decision-making skills[17].

In particular, it has been confirmed that the teacher's creation of a positive psychological environment during the lesson is an important factor in ensuring the active participation of students. A positive environment is not just a happy or relaxed atmosphere, but a learning environment that is based on mutual respect, support, fair assessment, and equal opportunities. In such conditions, students feel safe and are fully engaged in the learning process.

CONCLUSION

1. The results of the study showed that the interest of primary school students in mathematics is a complex and multi-factorial pedagogical process, in which interactive methods, didactic games and digital educational tools occupy a leading place. These approaches increase the cognitive activity of students and serve to develop their logical thinking, independent work, problem-solving and creative approach skills. In particular, it was confirmed through empirical results that lessons organized on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies are more effective than traditional approaches.

2. The research revealed that the teacher's pedagogical skills, communicative competence and individual approach are of decisive importance in forming interest in mathematics. The teacher's use of stimulating methods, creating a positive psychological environment and taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students significantly increase their motivation for the lesson. Also, effective communication between the teacher and the student improves the quality of the educational process and increases the activity of students.

3. In general, the results of the study showed the need to systematically introduce interactive, innovative and digital approaches to improve the teaching process of mathematics in primary education. An educational environment organized on the basis of cooperation between the family, school and teacher sustainably develops students' interest in mathematics and increases their intellectual potential. Therefore, the integrated use of modern methods in mathematics education is one of the most important areas for improving the quality and effectiveness of education.

REFERENCES

1. Jumayev, M. E. (2005). *Methodology of teaching mathematics in primary grades*. Tashkent: Science and Technology. 312 p.
2. Jumayev, M. E. (2016). *Methodology of teaching mathematics*. Tashkent: Turon-Iqbol. 280 p.
3. Bikboyeva, N. U., Yangiboyeva, E., & Gafforova, K. (2014). *Methodology of teaching mathematics in primary grades*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi. 295 p.
4. Nishonova, Z. T. (2018). *Pedagogy of primary education*. Tashkent: Fan. 260 p.
5. Hasanboeva, O., Nishonova, Z., & Jorayeva, M. (2019). *Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical mastery*. Tashkent: Science and Technology. 310 p.
6. Abduqodirov, A. (2017). *Information technologies in education*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi. 240 p.
7. Sattorova, I. (2020). *Methodology of teaching mathematics*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 220 p.
8. Tursunov, S. (2016). *Fundamentals of pedagogical technologies*. Tashkent: Fan. 200 p.
9. Karimova, N. (2021). *Using game technologies in primary grades*. Tashkent. 180 p.
10. Qodirov, A. (2019). *Modern educational technologies*. Tashkent: Ilm Ziyo. 250 p.
11. Avloniy, A. (2004). *Turkic Gulistan, or ethics* (Reprint). Tashkent: O'qituvchi. 120 p.
12. Republic of Uzbekistan. (2020). *Law on Education*. Tashkent.
13. Republic of Uzbekistan. (2021). *State Educational Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Primary education*. Tashkent.
14. Mirziyoyev, Sh. M. (2017–2024). *Speeches and resolutions on the development of the education system*. Tashkent.
15. Urazova, S. O. (2023). *Teaching mathematics in primary grades through interactive methods*. Scientific article.

16. Imomova, N. (2024). *The use of digital technologies in primary education*. Scientific journal. Tadqiqotlar.uz.
17. Ortiqboyeva, S. O. (2023). *The effectiveness of interactive methods and didactic games in primary grades*. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*.